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Staff Motivation And Supervision As Correlates Of Teachers Job Productivity In Public Secondary Schools In Ebonyi State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated Staff motivation and supervision as correlates of teachers' job productivity in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State. Two research questions and two hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. Correlational design was adopted for this study. Population of the study comprised all the 3,983 (comprising 222 principals and 3,761 teachers) in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State. The sample size comprised 501 respondents using the Taro Yamane sample size formula. Two validated self-structured instruments titled, Staff Motivation and Supervision Scale (SMAS) and Teachers' Job Productivity Scale (TJPS) were used for data collection. Cronbachs' alpha statistics was used to establish the reliability coefficient of both instruments which yielded 0.73 and 0.79 respectively. Research questions were answered using Pearson Product Moment Correlation while hypotheses were tested using z-ratio and analysis of variance associated with multiple regression at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that staff motivation and supervision have a strong and moderate correlations with teacher's job productivity in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State. Based on findings, it was concluded that staff motivation and supervision have significant positive relationship on teacher's job productivity in public secondary schools in Ebonyi state. It was therefore, recommended that public secondary school management in Ebonyi State, make conscious effort to motivate their teachers at all times in order to increase their job productivity.

Keywords: Staff Motivation, Staff Supervision, Teachers, Job Productivity

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The success of the school system, like any other organization is anchored on providing good and enabling working environment geared towards the advancement of productive capacities of staff at work. These capacities are in the pursuit of achieving the educational objectives as well as satisfying the needs of the individual staff. The primary aim of school personnel management is to secure sufficient numbers and categories of suitable teachers and support staff to undertake the task of educating the students to the standard expected by the students, their parents and the society at large. Thus, the quality of education provided in schools depends directly on the capability, commitment and motivation of the teachers together with significant number of non-teaching staff employed in a variety of support roles. According to Bua and Ada (2018), personnel management is a continuous process that involves team spirit and team work. The scholars further add that it involves functions like planning, organizing, directing and controlling, procurement, development, maintenance of human resources and helps to achieve individual, organizational and social objectives. According to Omebe (2001), teachers who are well managed always look for better ways of performing their job of teaching. Such teachers are more quality oriented and more productive. Armstrong (2000), defines performance appraisals as a systematic way of evaluating a worker's performance and his potential for development. Performance appraisal is done on staff because they contribute to the attainment of

educational objectives. Decenzo and Robbison (2002) noted that, setting and communicating appraisal objectives creates clarity in the minds of the employees given the fact that members of staff have the opportunities to talk about the organizational objectives and to define their contributions to the achievement of those objectives

Ways Staff Motivation by Personnel Managers Enhance Teachers' Productivity

Motivation is associated with productivity. It is a process by which people are equally managed to satisfy their basic drives, perceived needs and personal goals which trigger off human behaviours and personal development. Motivation may also be seen as the willingness to exert high levels of efforts towards organizational goals conditioned by the efforts to satisfy some individual and societal needs. Motivation of academic staff is a strategic force that would reduce tension, stress, worries and frustration arising from the academic environment for quality service delivery. Also this enhances teaching staff functions for effective curriculum implementation in secondary schools. Iyeke (2013) sees motivation as a management function that stimulates individuals to accomplish laid down institutional goals. Peretomode (1991) opined that teachers' motivation related to a purposive and goal directed behavior, performance and attitude towards work. It includes considering such factors as psychological and environmental differences of individual employees. It also leads to job satisfaction which is defined as the feelings (either good or bad) one has about his/her work and the work environment. According to Peretomode (1991) motivation is the process of influencing or stimulating a person to take action that will accomplish desired goals. Frederickson (2004) re-emphasized the importance of motivating teachers on their jobs using a study conducted by the Voluntary Service Overseas (VSO) in 2002, whose research report findings pointed out that teachers' motivation was fragile and declining mostly in the developing countries including Nigeria. The study also observed that poor absolute value of the teachers' salaries was significant factor influencing their motivation. Low salaries and bad working conditions always breed corruption. The research report findings also noted that "there is a strong link between teachers' motivation and quality performance and quality education, all involve in guaranteeing quality assurance in the Nigerian educational system. Therefore, teachers' contribution towards learning is strongly influenced by teacher motivation and motivation which includes good working conditions, promotion, staff training and development, good salary and remuneration, participatory decision making, job security, recognition of performances and the teaching profession, financial rewards, scholarships and awards and provision of other facilities are strong tools for improving the status of teacher." Teachers' motivation has great significance or value to the Nigerian educational system in guaranteeing quality assurance. When teachers are highly motivated and adequate attention given to them, it adds value and quality to the educational system by raising its standards to rise to the expected level thereby ensuring quality teaching-learning outcomes and output.

Ways Staff Supervision by Personnel Managers Enhance Teachers' productivity

The process of supervision in secondary schools in Nigeria are paramount to the attainment of effective monitoring for national development and the administration of the schools entirely. Supervision is an indispensable variable in the teaching-learning process as well as in the actualization of the overall school and educational objectives as it helps teachers achieve both qualitative and quantitative instructional delivery. According to Bernard and Goodyear (1992), supervision is the relationship between the superior and subordinate workers in an organization which evaluates over a period of time, helps to uplift the skills of subordinates, monitors the quantity/quality of job they do, and provide necessary feedback for further action. In other words, supervision means managing others by provision of exemplary actions. Loganbill et al. (1982) views supervision as a serious and important interpersonal relationship whereby a person plays a role in the development of other persons within an organization. Glickman et al. (2004) believes that supervision is the means of controlling the behavior of workers. Kimosop (2002), instructional supervision is an expert technical service primarily concerned with studying and improving learning and pupils' growth. We can also define instructional supervision as the set of activities designed to improve the teaching-learning process. According to Bernard and Goodyear (1992), supervision is the relationship between the superior and subordinate workers in an organization which evaluates over a period of time, helps to uplift the skills of subordinates, monitors the quantity/quality of job they do, and provide necessary feedback for further action. In other words, supervision means managing others by provision of

exemplary actions. Loganbill et al. (1982) views supervision as a serious and important interpersonal relationship whereby a person plays a role in the development of other persons within an organization. Glickman et al. (2004) believes that supervision is the means of controlling the behavior of workers. In such case, the workers are inspected and guided in their daily activities. Here, the emphasis is on constant compliance by the workers with the rules of the organization. This usually hinders the development of innovative abilities and creativity on job. McGregor (1989), posited that supervision enables the overall achievement of organizational performance, he asserted that if you want to improve employee performance, think about your daily conversations with employees. No better opportunity exists to reinforce and help refer excellent employee performance. You discuss new projects, talk about overdue assignments, give updates about completed tasks, and more. To this extent, organizational citizen behavior research findings have encouraged educational institutions to improve supervisors' attitude and behavior in order to increase the performance of the supervisees (de Geus et al., 2020).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The school system just like any organization's overall objective is to utilize the available human and material resources for the purpose of producing quality output at minimal cost. The realization of the goal depends on how personnel management is able to contribute meaningfully and effectively to the successful achievement of the corporate goals of the school through management of the staff to perform their functions in the enabling work environment. It has been ascertained that personnel management and administration is sine qua non for the success of any organization particularly, secondary education.

However, the researcher observed that personnel management in public senior secondary schools in Ebonyi State is witnessing some changes in concept and practice as no adequate measures are put in place to ensure quality welfare of the staff. Most of the teachers work in deplorable conditions, inadequate staff appraisal, uncoordinated transfer policies, inadequate good health care scheme, inadequate supervision, no proper staff mentorship, inadequate staff motivation, amongst others. These working conditions, make their morale level low as can be seen in their attitude towards work and the performance of their students in both internal and external examinations. Therefore, the researcher investigated what relationship would exist between staff motivation, staff supervision and teachers job productivity in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State

1.3 Aim and Objectives of the Study

Specific objectives are to;

1. Ascertain the relationship between staff motivation by personnel managers and teachers' job productivity in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State.
2. Determine the relationship between staff supervision by personnel managers and teachers' job productivity in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State.

1.4 Research Questions

The research questions includes:

1. What is the relationship between staff motivation by personnel managers and teachers' job productivity in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State?
2. What is the relationship between staff supervision by personnel managers and teachers' job productivity in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State?

1.5 Hypotheses

H1 There is no significant relationship between staff motivation and teachers' job productivity in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State.

H2 there is no significant relationship between staff supervision and teachers 'job productivity in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The design for this study was the correlational design. The population for this study comprised all the 3,983 principals and teachers in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State. There are two hundred and twenty two (222) secondary schools in both the urban and rural parts of the state. The respondents were drawn from the three thousand, seven hundred and sixty one (3,761) teachers and two hundred and twenty two (222) principals in public secondary schools both in the urban and rural areas of the

state. The sample of the study was 501 public secondary school personnel's (139 principals and 362 teachers). The Taro Yamane minimum sample size determination formular was used to determine the sample size for the study. The researcher designed a two (2) self-structured instrument. The first instrument that was used for data collection for the study contained 60 items titled 'Staff Motivation and Supervision Scale' (SMSS) which was used to elicit responses on the independent variable of the study. The data that were gathered from the field were collected, and analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation to answer research questions one to two while research question was answered using multiple regression. Hypotheses one to two were tested using z-ratio.

4.0 RESULTS

4.1 Research question 1: *What is the relationship between staff motivation by personnel managers and teachers' job productivity in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State?*

Table 4.1: Pearson Product Moment of the relationship between staff motivation by personnel managers and teachers' job productivity

Variables	N	r	Decision
Staff motivation			
Teachers' productivity	501	0.887	Positive high relationship

Data on table 4.1 revealed that Pearson Product Moment correlation coefficient is given as 0.887. This shows that there is a positive and high relationship between staff motivation by personnel managers and teachers' job productivity in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State. Therefore, an increase in staff motivation personnel managers leads to a corresponding increase in teachers' job productivity in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State.

4.2 Research question 2: *What is the relationship between staff supervision by personnel managers and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State?*

Table 4.2: Pearson Product Moment of the relationship between staff supervision by personnel managers and teachers' job productivity

Variables	N	r	Decision
Staff supervision			
Teachers' productivity	501	0.564	Positive moderate relationship

Data on table 4.2 revealed that Pearson Product Moment correlation coefficient is given as 0.567. This shows that there is a positive and moderately high relationship between staff supervision by personnel managers and teachers' job productivity in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State. Therefore, an increase in staff supervision personnel managers leads to a corresponding increase in teachers' job productivity in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State.

4.3 Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between staff motivation and teachers' job productivity in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State.

Table 4.3: z-ratio of the relationship between staff motivation by personnel managers and teachers' job productivity

Variables	N	R	Df	z-ratio	Sig.	Alpa value	Decision
Staff motivation							H₀ was Rejected
Teachers' productivity	501	0.887	499	48.38	0.00	0.05	

Data on table 4.3 shows that the z-ratio value is 48.38 with a degree of freedom of 499. The hypothesis is rejected because the significant value of 0.00 is less than the alpha value of 0.05. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between staff motivation and teachers' job productivity in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State.

4.4 Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between staff supervision and teachers' job productivity in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State.

Table 4.4: z-ratio of the relationship between staff supervision by personnel managers and teachers' job productivity

Variables	N	R	Df	z-ratio	Sig.	Alpa value	Decision
Staff supervision							H ₀ was rejected
Teachers' productivity	501	0.564	499	27.05	0.00	0.05	

Data on table 4.4 shows that the z-ratio value is 27.05 with the degree of freedom of 499. The hypothesis is rejected because the significant value of 0.00 is less than the alpha value of 0.05. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between staff supervision and teachers' job productivity in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State.

4.5 DISCUSSION OF FINDING

Staff motivation by personnel managers and teachers' job productivity in public secondary schools.

From the result gotten, it means that motivation of teachers' ensures quality teaching and learning, motivation of teachers' enhances job satisfaction, motivation of teachers' guarantees quality assurance in the educational system, motivation of teachers' sustains and directs positive behavior, motivation of teachers' reduces frustration which may arise from the work environment, motivation of teachers encourages them to try out new instructional strategies, motivation of teachers make them laid back, motivation of teachers lessens frustration and brings respect to the teaching work itself, motivation of teachers enriches teachers attitude to the teaching job, and motivation of teachers lead to high productivity account for 89% of teacher's job productivity in public secondary school. This shows that there is a positive high relationship between staff motivation by personnel managers and teachers' job productivity in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State. Therefore, an increase in staff motivation personnel managers leads to a corresponding increase in teachers' job productivity in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State. This finding is in line with Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory on motivation who suggested that in order to motivate employees and enhance job satisfaction, organizations should not only focus on providing adequate hygiene factors but also emphasize the presence of motivators. Also, this finding is in accordance with the assertions of Lyke (2013) who argued that motivation stimulates to accomplish laid down institutional goals. No wonder, scholars see it as the process of instigating and sustaining goal directed behavior (Pintrinch & Schunk, 2008). Bahago (2011) supports this claim by noting that it is a purposely designated goal- oriented behaviour that involves certain forces to act on or within the individual in order to initiate, sustain or direct behavior.

Peretomede (1991) corroborated the above findings and assertions in the scholar's argument that teachers should be motivated in order to boost their productivity, effectiveness, efficiency and dedication in performing their task, which will enhance quality assurance, quality education and quality instructional delivery in the educational system. Motivation of teachers' help to empower them and also enhance the achievement of educational objectives. It includes considering such factors as the psychological, physiological and environmental conduciveness. These findings also agrees with Pilot (2007) who adumbrated motivation to include good working conditions, promotion, staff training and development, good salary and remuneration, participatory decision making, job security, recognition of performances, financial rewards, scholarships and awards, provision of other facilities which are strong tools for improving the status of teachers. The test of hypothesis also agree with this finding

Staff supervision by personnel managers and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools

The result from this findings, imply that supervision of teachers' helps in the achievement of educational objectives, supervision of teachers' promotes superordinate/subordinate co-operation, supervision of teachers' ensures that high standards are maintained, supervision of teachers' leads to improvement in instruction, supervision of teachers' helps to identify and proffer solutions to

problems, supervision puts a lot of pressure on teachers, supervision serves as a tool of guidance to teachers, supervision helps the heads of the educational systems to know the infrastructures lacking, supervision improves the quality of education as it makes the educational system not to be loose, supervision is a powerful tool that helps the level of success a school has achieved in terms of learning and otherwise account for 57% of teacher's productivity in Public Secondary school. This shows that there is a positive and moderate relationship between staff supervision by personnel managers and teachers' job productivity in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State. Again, data on table 4.2 shows that with the degree of freedom of 499 the hypothesis is rejected because the significant value of 0.00 is less than the alpha value of 0.05. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between staff supervision and teachers' job productivity in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State. By implication, an increase in staff supervision personnel managers leads to a moderate corresponding increase in teachers' job productivity in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State. This finding is in line with Ma and Boldureanu (2020) who opined that the general attitude of supervisors usually have major positive moderating effect on the association between workers' attitude and job performance especially in educational institutions. Akinwumiju and Agabi (2008) also corroborated the findings here when they concluded that supervision is designed to achieve improvement in instruction, resolution of school constraints, maintenance of superordinate-subordinate co-operation, professionalism and autonomy of staff and achievement of intrinsic motivation. On the overall, supervision provides opportunities to access the challenges confronting the school and the level of success achieved in the pursuit of school goals.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that staff motivation as well as Staff supervision have positive significant impact on teacher's productivity in public secondary school in Ebonyi state, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Public secondary school management in Ebonyi state should make conscious effort to motivate their teachers at all time in order to increase high productivity
- Secondary school management should ensure regular supervision of teachers in order to achieve educational objectives

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